

Application of Drone Technology in Horticulture

Dr. G.Vaidehi

Associate Professor, School of Agriculture,
Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research

Abstract

The population is increasing tremendously and with this increase the demand of food. The traditional methods which were used by the farmers were not sufficient enough to fulfil these requirements. Thus, new automated methods (Drone technology) were introduced. These new methods satisfied the food requirements and also provided employment opportunities to billions of people. Drones' technologies save the excess use of water, pesticides, and herbicides, maintains the fertility of the soil, also helps in the efficient use of man power and elevate the productivity and improve the quality. The objective of this paper is to review the usage of Drones in Horticulture applications. Based on the literature, we found that a lot of agriculture applications can be done by using Drone. In the methodology, we used a comprehensive review from other researches in this world. This paper summarizes the current state of drone technology for agricultural uses, including crop health monitoring

Introduction

An industry of value, Agriculture sets the livelihood of 65% of the population of India, directly or indirectly. The vitality of the Agricultural Industry is so deep-rooted in our systems that its growth heavily affects the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of our country by about 17%. Heightening this growth factor has become ever-so-crucial to generate more revenue, income, and employment. The dynamic and speedy nature of technology brings convenience and advancement to its applied industries. Drone technology and the

Soil Health Monitoring The robust capabilities of drones help in the primitive operation of analysing soil health. In essence, UAVs collect and process data received from monitoring that can help check, control, and maintain the soil's health and nature.

Drone technology can also provide the essential nutrients to the soil to improve their health and well-being. Through its operations of 3D mapping and data processing, drones achieve this operation of analysing soil health. **Seeding Process** By its virtue, agriculture is a highly cumbersome and exhaustive industry because it requires skilful abilities to perform its operations. Seeding, especially, requires manual labour as it is a time-consuming procedure.

To ease this tiring process, drone technology is employed to sow the seeds of the copious varieties of crops. As instilled in drones, the lasers, sensors, tanks, etc., allow them to quickly yet smoothly plant seeds.

Analyzing

Deficiencies

Another incredible merit of adopting drones for crop fertilization comes with their feature to analyze, identify, and survey the crops for any deficiencies. Their high-resolution cameras and sensors, additionally instilled with lasers, help to perform these operations quickly. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles can also map these deficiencies in real-time, and the data collected and processed can be used to make further determinations regarding the crops.

Drones for Crop Fertilization In its entirety, drones and their applications have helped ease the cumbersome process attributed to crop fertilization. Their enterprising and potent nature helps farmers a great deal with bountiful tasks and operations.

Plantation

Drones can help in planting trees and crops, which was done by farmers before. This technology will not only save labor but also help in saving fuels. Soon, it is expected that budget friendly drones will be used instead of huge tractors, as they emit harmful gases and pollute the environment in the process.

Benefits of Horti-drones

Security: The drones are operated by trained drone pilots. So, there are no chances of their misuse. High efficiency: Drones do not have any operational delays and can work double the speed of human labor

Drones, for starters, are great for monitoring and sensing techniques because they can quickly cover territory to check crop development and soil health. Drones are mostly used for this purpose since their sensors can detect the absorbance of a specific wavelength, resulting in a color contrast image that visibly reflects possibly problematic locations. Ranchers have also employed drones to track livestock on ranches and check for any damaged fences, demonstrating that this monitoring capability not only provides for rapid processing of spatiotemporal information. Rangers have also employed night cameras and thermal imagers to locate any animals disturbing or attacking herds to better monitor cattle.

The second major use of drones in agriculture is to keep crops healthy by dispersing water, fertilizer, and pesticides. Drones coupled with spectroscopic and thermography technology can detect dry areas and address problems that traditional watering equipment may have missed. Drones, on the other hand, can detect equipment leaks and irrigation problems. Drones can stitch thermographic photos together over time to detect the direction of water flow and locate geographical features that may affect water dispersion. Drones' accuracy and speed allow fertilizer to be delivered to precise locations if crops aren't growing well enough, as well as the elimination of pests and pathogens by spraying pesticides from the drones themselves.

A third significant benefit of drones is that they can operate as mechanical pollinators. Although insect vectors are still the most important pollinators, drones may one day replace bees as the most essential pollinators. Although further research is needed in this area, researchers are optimistic that drones will be able to another important aspect of drone application is the use of drones for agricultural research. Drones can cover broad areas damaged by natural catastrophes to find the reasons and implications of incidents, from infections to insurance claims.

Drones are already being used to confirm claims in agricultural insurance surveys, and the quick response paired with high-resolution imaging allows for the collection of data on huge scales, which is difficult, if not impossible, to do on the same timescale with manual labor. Drones are a good contender for enhancing agricultural techniques at a low cost because of these advantages. Aside from the financial benefits, optimizing fertilizer, pesticide, and water usage in important areas has various ecological and environmental benefits that would not be feasible otherwise.

References

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